

Perceptions and attitudes of senior high school students towards online learning

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Abstract

Online learning enables the students to explore varied opportunities that will help enhance their skills and knowledge. Through different technological tools and applications, it is important for students to access the different lessons that will be applicable for their needs and interests and also for their future professional careers. This study investigated the perceptions and attitudes of Senior High School students towards online learning. The research also determined the positive and negative aspects of online learning that were encountered by Senior High School learners. Overall, one hundred thirty-nine (139) Senior High School students took part in the study. The results showed that students have mostly positive level of perceptions and attitudes. It is indicated that the students got high mean scores in all five scales: technology experiences and challenges, teacher's interaction with students, quality of student's work, autonomy and student engagement, and home support and assistance, including the general perceptions of the online learning. Most students positively focused on developing new skills and knowledge, while denoting that they also experienced technical problems such as unstable internet connection and lack of access. Apart from using new tools and participating in activities that are suited to their needs and desires, encouraging students to successfully expand their use of online learning can help them remain engaged. Future research should also include the impact of the present study to a larger size sample; thus, this will help other researchers to look into alternative ways of promoting effective and time-efficient virtual classrooms.

Keywords: Online learning. Senior High School (SHS). COVID-19 pandemic. Perceptions. Attitudes.

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Introduction

Education has been evolved over time and technologies have contributed to the changing landscape within the learners and instructors. With the rise of online learning tools, development of digital literacy skills extends beyond the learning which makes us more essential to our lives. The addition of technologies through the classroom changes our perspectives the way we see and understand them. With just a fingertip, information such as books, videos, and images can be accessible, which enable the people to increase their learning opportunities and enhance their communication and collaboration skills. According to Assareh and Bidokht (2011), education is not only limited to special places like schools; whereas all learners should be life-long learners regardless of time and place and new education should help students on what to learn and how to learn.

Even before the coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, many schools and universities use different online learning platforms in reaching out to students through an excellent learning environment suited to their needs and interests. Learners effectively utilize these tools to manage their time in submitting their works and to prepare for their future academic and professional careers. Adedoyin and Soykan (2020) stressed that despite the sudden shift of educational delivery to online platforms by universities and other learning centers, it is evident that online learning will be maintained, and education will become more hybrid, provided that the challenges faced by teachers and students are well-explored which transformed into opportunities.

Clark and Meyer (2016) defined e-learning as instruction delivered on a digital service such as desktop and laptop computers, tablets, and smartphones that needs to support learning; courses are provided in the form of spoken or printed text and pictures such as illustrations, photos, animations, or videos. Garrison (2017) described e-learning as an "open system that joins access to information and purposeful communication into a dynamic and intellectually challenging learning community by means of expanding education beyond efficient delivery or entertainment value". It does not only focus on surfing the Internet as an educational experience, but rather empowers the learners to fully integrate the benefits of personal freedom in relation to connectivity within its educational properties and the interests of students. E-learning is a personalized approach that focuses on the individual learner and includes self-paced instruction, different virtual activities, mentoring, simulation, collaboration, assessment, competency road map, authoring resources, e-store, and learning management framework (Basak et al., 2018).

Today, online learning becomes necessary for students as different schools all over the world are looking some alternative ways to continue their learning the best that they can. This kind of learning allow both students and teachers to choose what learning style and approach could fit in their discussions and activities, may it be synchronous or asynchronous.

Yilmaz (2017) said that it is important to assess students' readiness for e-learning; as a result, it helps to provide them with training that will enable them to improve their knowledge and skills, as well as gain experience with the topics covered by online lessons. The media and online applications that will be used in online classes should have clear and easy-to-use features that will enable students to improve their self-efficacy and understand the usefulness of the technologies (Yilmaz, 2017).

Although online learning makes it easier for students and teachers to become more flexible in accomplishing their subjects successfully, barriers may come across in terms of adopting to the virtual environment and switching to a new curriculum. Many of them find it difficult to adapt this new method as they believed that traditional learning is more effective than digital and online learning in creating a learning atmosphere with great learning outcomes. Such reasons are due to lack of social interaction and too much exposure to screens such as smartphones, televisions, and laptops. Since digital and online learning become their sole means of communication with their teachers and peers, parents were concerned that learning online for children may cause a deterioration of eye vision and a decrease of their learning interest (Dong et al., 2020). Another reason is that students were also prone to distractions brought by the conflicts between their family members, and more time spent at home were focused than in academic works which they found it difficult to communicate with their parents or siblings about their concerns (Baticulon et al., 2021). In developing countries such as India and the Philippines, the transition to online learning is hindered by their reliance on technology and the lack of steady Internet access which is really a strong need for improvement to enhance the capacities of both students and teachers (Baloran, 2020; Kamble et al., 2021).

Learners and educators even the content itself all face challenges when it comes to online learning. With this, the task for institutions is to involve students and make them participate in the teaching-learning process, and teachers can move from offline to online mode so that they can adapt to various teaching methodologies and manage their time efficiently (Dhawan, 2020).

This study seeks to investigate the perceptions and attitudes of Senior High School students towards online learning. The research also seeks to identify the positive and negative aspects of online learning that were encountered by the Senior High School learners. The findings of the research study are intended to determine if online learning would benefit the Senior High School students efficiently in light of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methodology

A study design among one hundred and thirty-nine (139) Senior High School students was conducted in two (2) schools in Cavite to determine the perceptions and attitudes towards online learning. For each school, participants were randomly selected based on their availability and desire to participate in this research.

The main gathering instrument is a questionnaire which consisted of seven-point Likert-type attitude scales and an essay. The first part of the questionnaire was composed of six (6) scales which were subjected for the data collection of the participants: technology experiences and challenges (8 items); teacher's interaction with students (9 items); quality of student's work (7 items); autonomy in online class and student engagement (23 items); and home support and assistance (5 items). This was followed by fourteen (14) items related with the general views on online engagement. These statements enabled the students to rate the degree of agreement in each item (7 – strongly agree; 6 – agree; 5 – moderately agree; 4 – neutral; 3 – moderately disagree; 2 – disagree; and 1 – strongly disagree).

The second part consisted of two essay questions wherein respondents were allowed to write their opinions if online learning has been helpful to them. This study highlighted the positive and negative outcomes that brought by the senior high school students.

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The test was conducted for two weeks during the month of December 2020. An e-mail attached with an online link (Google Forms) was sent to two principals in respective schools to distribute the survey to their learners in their e-learning platforms. By clicking on the link, participants were asked to complete the questionnaire which would take approximately five to ten minutes. Data collection was done using a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet was also used to generate the data that were answered by the respondents.

Data were interpreted and analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel version 2016 for the descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage; weighted mean). Descriptive statistics was used to determine the level of attitudes and views of Senior High School students. A thematic analysis was formed to identify the positive and negative aspects that they encountered during their online learning.

Demographic Profile

Table 1 shows the overall demographic profile of the Senior High School students. Out of the 139 Senior High School students, majority or 80.58% of the participants were studying in a private school, while 19.42% from the public school. Thirty-five (35) students (25.18%) were studying in Grade 11, whereas one hundred and four (104) participants (74.82%) in Grade 12. Most of the respondents were females (70.50%), while the rest were males (29.50%). It was noted that many students were from the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand (40.29%); followed by Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) (38.13%), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) (20.14%), and Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) (1.44%).

Table 1. Overall demographic profile of the Senior High School students (n=139)

	Category	n	%
School	Private	112	80.58
	Public	27	19.42
Grade Level	Grade 11	35	25.18
	Grade 12	104	74.82
Gender	Female	98	70.50
	Male	41	29.50
Strand / Track	STEM	56	40.29
	ABM	53	38.13
	HUMSS	28	20.14
	TVL	2	1.44

Results and Discussion

The perceptions of students related to technology experiences and challenges are shown in Table 2. Based on the data, majority of the students “agree” that they find e-mails useful in their online learning (Mean=5.84). They also perceived that the lessons provided by the teacher are accessible and can be downloaded (Mean=5.66); and that they find different websites such as Quipper, Google Classroom, Facebook, and Messenger useful in their online learning (Mean=5.72).

It is seen that the lowest mean scores were observed in “not usually encountering technical problems during online class” for both schools. As compared to private school students who perceived it as “neutral” (Mean=3.50), public school students “moderately disagree” (Mean=3.41) that technical problems do not happen during their online learning.

This finding supports Corbera et al. (2020), which explained that many students (particularly in the developing countries) are struggling to engage with the online learning due to the lack of access to the requisite computer and network infrastructure, such as the high-speed internet; therefore, students experience unstable internet connections or do not have inadequate working spaces at home that may distract their participation in the online classes. This concern may find learners difficult to catch up with the lessons that they attend and even seek help from the Management Information Systems Department for some technical assistance. Nonetheless, it is important that emerging technologies such as the use of social media applications (e.g. Facebook, YouTube, Tiktok) can empower students by allowing them to share critical information and provide relevant feedback in the virtual world, which can speed up the information sharing process, particularly during pandemics (Toquero & Talidong, 2021). This will help not only the students and teachers but also the institutions to improve their access by making the courses more engaging and interesting.

Table 2. Students’ perceptions related to technology experiences and challenges

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. The online delivery of our class or subject is convenient.	4.87	Moderately Agree	5.00	Moderately Agree
2. Our internet connection is adequate.	4.19	Neutral	4.33	Neutral
3. The virtual tools are easy to use or navigate.	4.84	Moderately Agree	4.78	Moderately Agree
4. I don't usually encounter technical problems (e.g. Unstable network, audio or visual problems) during online class.	3.50	Neutral	3.41	Moderately Disagree
5. The lessons provided by the teacher are accessible and can be downloaded.	5.61	Agree	5.70	Agree
6. Recorded videos of our lessons are uploaded on time.	4.86	Moderately Agree	4.70	Moderately Agree
7. I find different websites (e.g. Quipper, Google Classroom, Facebook, and Messenger) useful in online learning.	5.54	Agree	5.89	Agree
8. I find e-mails useful in online learning.	5.75	Agree	6.11	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

With regards to the interaction of students with their teachers (Table 3), most of the students “agree” that teachers do their best to deliver online learning effectively by giving them online activities related to their course and subject (Mean=5.89); by discussing virtually (Mean=5.84); and by using video presentations with visuals and sounds (Mean=5.84). and online activities (Mean=6.00).

It is also revealed that students mostly “agree” that their teachers provide review materials for them to study lessons at their homes (Mean=5.86), provide flexibility in all deadlines (Mean=5.59); and give them enough time to complete their homework. These results are in congruence with the study of Martin et al., (2012) wherein the virtual classroom helps both students and teachers to improve learner-learner, learner-instructor, learner-content, and learner-interface interaction and address their understanding of the instructional concepts in an online setting, even in asynchronous classes.

Table 3. Students' perceptions related to interaction with their teachers

Our teachers are doing their best to deliver online learning effectively by	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. uploading a complete set of modules.	5.41	Moderately Agree	6.11	Agree
2. providing flexibility in all deadlines.	5.18	Moderately Agree	5.59	Agree
3. giving me enough time to complete our homework and online activities.	5.09	Moderately Agree	6.00	Agree
4. providing review materials (e.g. Soft copy of lectures, exercises, educational videos, recordings) for us to study our lessons at home.	5.60	Agree	5.48	Moderately Agree
5. giving us online activities related to our course and subject.	5.63	Agree	6.15	Agree
6. discussing virtually.	5.97	Agree	5.70	Agree
7. using video presentations (i.e. with visual and sound).	5.97	Agree	5.70	Agree
8. I can easily ask questions to my teachers and receive a quick response through online.	5.27	Moderately Agree	5.26	Moderately Agree
9. There is an immediate feedback on assessed activities or major exams.	5.02	Moderately Agree	5.11	Moderately Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

Social interaction towards their teachers and co-learners can increase their motivation, engagement, and performance to create a deeper understanding and knowledge in the course content through communication. They can even share their own experiences and perceptions of certain course concepts or post their concerns in discussion boards. Collaboration is also essential because it helps students to succeed with their goals and objectives and prepare themselves for their professional careers.

In Table 4, the attitudes of students related to quality of work were displayed. The results revealed that students "agree" in making sure that they cite references properly on their papers (Mean=5.79); in making more comprehensive notes for their online courses (Mean=5.63); in carefully following the guidelines for submission of requirements set by the subject and the teacher (Mean=6.14); and in making sure that they submit their work on time (Mean=5.81).

It is also noted that most of the public school students "agree" that they use search engines in verifying their answers (Mean=5.96) and that they use books and other materials for their references (Mean=5.52).

In a similar study by Tai et al. (2018), the researchers conducted on developing evaluative judgment which enabled students to make decisions about the quality of work. Tai et al. said that evaluative judgement puts these various activities together and refocuses them as pedagogies to produce students who can make good judgments both inside and outside of the course; thus self- and peer-review exercises in which students judge their own work and that of others could be used to determine if evaluative judgment has evolved. This will make it easier for students to manage their time and study independently in keeping track of their assignments and working on their course materials before or on the deadlines.

Table 4. Students' attitudes related to quality of work

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. I make sure that I cite references properly on my paper.	6.06	Agree	5.52	Agree
2. I try to make more comprehensive notes for my online courses.	5.58	Agree	5.67	Agree
3. In submitting the requirements, I carefully follow the guidelines set by the subject and the teacher.	6.08	Agree	6.19	Agree
4. I summarize my learning in online course to examine my own understanding on the different subjects.	5.40	Moderately Agree	5.48	Moderately Agree
5. I use search engines in verifying my answers.	4.97	Moderately Agree	5.96	Agree
6. I use books and other materials for my references.	4.95	Moderately Agree	5.52	Agree
7. I make sure that I submit work on time.	6.10	Agree	5.52	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

As seen in Table 5 which is the attitudes of students related to autonomy and online engagement, public school students had large mean scores than the private school students. These scores are noticed that the students “agree” in setting goals to prepare themselves for online courses (Mean=5.63); in setting goals to manage studying time for their online courses (Mean=5.93); in choosing a comfortable place to study (Mean=5.52); in creating a schedule for studying to pass their subject (Mean=5.56); that their preparation for major examinations is more challenging than before (Mean=5.93); that their learning styles have adjusted to the online teaching method (Mean=5.70); that they do resting when they feel discomfort in their eyes and body (Mean=6.07); and in becoming more responsible for their own learning (Mean=5.52).

Two statements such as “in finding the workload in online equally as in face-to-face classes” and “that online lessons are more flexible than in the traditional classes” had their smallest mean scores respectively in private and public school students.

However, it is implied that public school students “moderately disagree” that they could still study and accomplish their assignments at their own pace and time (Mean=3.15).

These results corroborate with the study of Martin and Bolliger (2018) that as demonstrated by their relatively high ratings for items such as grading rubrics, checklists, forums, and student orientations, students expected their teachers to assist them in their learning and construct meaningful learning experiences which would increase their engagement to support their interaction and facilitation. This enables the learners to be more active when they perform best in ensuring that their tasks will be organized in the right place at the right time. Students learn efficiently by promoting their self-regulation to improve the mastery of the learning tasks given to them.

Table 5. Students’ attitudes related to autonomy and online engagement

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. I set goals to prepare myself for online courses.	5.46	Moderately Agree	5.63	Agree
2. I set goals to manage studying time for my online courses.	5.38	Moderately Agree	5.93	Agree
3. In online class, I can choose a comfortable place to study.	5.21	Moderately Agree	5.52	Agree
4. I have a schedule for studying to pass my subject.	4.85	Moderately Agree	5.56	Agree
5. Online delivery gives me control of my learning styles.	4.79	Moderately Agree	5.04	Moderately Agree
6. I find online activities easy to answer and react.	4.35	Neutral	4.96	Moderately Agree
7. I have acquired the learning skills set by the subject or course.	4.96	Moderately Agree	5.22	Moderately Agree
8. I have acquired the knowledge set by the subject or course.	5.14	Moderately Agree	5.26	Moderately Agree
9. Online lessons are more flexible than in the traditional classes.	3.69	Neutral	3.15	Moderately Disagree
10. During asynchronous classes, I can choose the time to study whenever I want.	5.23	Moderately Agree	4.93	Moderately Agree
11. I spend more time studying my lessons in online than in traditional mode.	4.49	Neutral	4.33	Neutral
12. In online classes, my preparation for major examinations is more challenging than before.	5.45	Moderately Agree	5.93	Agree
13. My learning styles have adjusted to the online teaching method.	5.31	Moderately Agree	5.70	Agree
14. I am now comfortable with the use of online platforms.	5.04	Moderately Agree	4.74	Moderately Agree
15. I have already adapted to online classes.	4.62	Moderately Agree	4.81	Moderately Agree
16. I find it easy to participate in online class discussions.	4.47	Neutral	4.11	Neutral
17. Online classes motivate me to study more.	3.71	Neutral	4.26	Neutral
18. It is easy to learn and understand from our lessons online.	3.72	Neutral	3.74	Neutral
19. I rest when I feel discomfort in my eyes and body.	4.50	Moderately Agree	6.07	Agree
20. I exercise, play sports, or watch a TV show to take a break after online classes and activities.	4.61	Moderately Agree	5.41	Moderately Agree
21. Online delivery will be helpful for the growth of my career.	4.31	Neutral	5.15	Moderately Agree
22. I become more responsible for my own learning.	5.38	Moderately Agree	5.52	Agree
23. I find the workload in online equally as in the face-to-face classes.	3.57	Neutral	4.67	Moderately Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

In Table 6, the attitudes of students related to home support and assistance were determined. The results showed that majority of the public school students “agree” that their parents monitor their attendance in asynchronous classes (Mean=5.52); whereas private school students are “neutral” in asking someone at home who is knowledgeable in technology when they need help (Mean=3.85). It is also revealed that the lowest mean scores were found in the statement “A member in the family joins or listens quietly during synchronous classes.” As opposed to public school students who are “neutral” in the said statement (Mean=3.70), it is implied that private school students parents do not usually join in the online learning and the students prefer to learn all by themselves.

In a same study by Curtis (2013) which investigated the parental involvement and student success in high school online education, the researcher revealed that parents were unable to motivate their children to take an active role in their own education in some occasions; therefore, students became often unsuccessful and struggled in these situations. He also noted that if students are unable to participate in their own education and their parents are unable to inspire them, an outside force, such as the school, is unlikely to be able to help. It is also important for parents or even family members to assist and motivate their children in getting involved with the online learning to increase their support and encouragement towards them. This motivation can help students to build a nurturing and positive learning environment and continue what they do best in the virtual classroom.

Table 6. Students’ attitudes related to home support and assistance

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. I ask someone at home who is knowledgeable in technology when I need help.	3.85	Neutral	4.96	Moderately Agree
2. My parents monitor my attendance in synchronous classes.	3.67	Neutral	5.30	Moderately Agree
3. My parents monitor my attendance during asynchronous classes.	3.37	Moderately Disagree	5.52	Agree
4. A member in the family joins or listens quietly during synchronous classes.	2.29	Disagree	3.70	Neutral
5. A member in the family makes suggestions to my output before final submission.	2.88	Moderately Disagree	4.15	Neutral

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 7 indicates the general perceptions of students towards online learning. The results showed that students “agree” in asking assistance from their classmates in terms of clarification in requirements (Mean=5.97). This statement had the highest mean scores for both private and public schools. For public school students, they “agree” that interacting with their classmates is fast and easy (Mean=5.63); they can listen to an online lecture (Mean=5.67); can collaborate and discuss with their classmates (Mean=5.56); and that online learning helps them to communicate more efficiently (Mean=5.52).

In contrast, it is evident for private school students that they are “neutral” in the statements “Online classes support my learning process” (Mean=4.48); “It helps me to communicate more efficiently” (Mean=4.46); “I become more confident in discussing a topic with my classmates” (Mean=4.38); and “I become more confident in discussing a topic with my teacher” (Mean=4.34). This means that students have “mixed” perceptions when online learning is implemented to the classrooms. Online learning allows more opportunities for students to take control of their styles and access the lessons and exercises even in offline mode.

Table 7. General perceptions of students towards online learning

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. I ask assistance from my classmates in terms of clarification in requirements.	5.87	Agree	6.07	Agree
2. I find my interaction with my classmates fast and easy.	5.04	Moderately Agree	5.63	Agree
3. I can participate in all class discussions.	4.73	Moderately Agree	5.04	Moderately Agree
4. I ask help from my teachers if I find it difficult in understanding the lessons.	4.71	Moderately Agree	5.44	Moderately Agree
5. I can complete an online activity as scheduled.	5.31	Moderately Agree	5.00	Moderately Agree
6. Activities are self-paced.	4.67	Moderately Agree	5.26	Moderately Agree
7. I can listen to an online lecture.	5.32	Moderately Agree	5.67	Agree
8. I can collaborate and discuss with my classmates.	5.13	Moderately Agree	5.56	Agree
9. Online classes support my learning process.	4.48	Neutral	5.22	Moderately Agree

	Private School		Public School	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
10. It helps me to communicate more efficiently.	4.46	Neutral	5.52	Agree
11. I become more confident in discussing a topic with my classmates.	4.38	Neutral	4.70	Moderately Agree
12. I become more confident in discussing a topic with my teacher.	4.34	Neutral	4.78	Moderately Agree
13. Online classes enhance my skills and creativity.	4.66	Moderately Agree	5.30	Moderately Agree
14. I can efficiently utilize my time.	4.51	Moderately Agree	5.33	Moderately Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Disagree); 3.50-4.49 (Neutral); 4.50-5.49 (Moderately Agree); 5.50-6.49 (Agree); 6.50-7.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 8 reveals the themes which came out of the responses about the positive aspects of online learning. One hundred and thirty-two (132) responses were collected on how online learning benefited as students. Based on the given data, majority of the students responded that online learning helps them to develop new skills and knowledge (n=40). This is followed by “managing time independently” (n=32); “added flexibility” (n=15); “improved virtual communication” (n=11); “safe and relaxing virtual environment” (n=11); “self-motivation” (n=8); “being more responsible” (n=7); “easy to adjust in the online learning” (n=5); and “rate of development similar with face-to-face classes” (n=1).

Table 8. Positive aspects of online learning (n=132)

No.	Responses	n
1	Developing new skills and knowledge	40
2	Managing time independently	32
3	Added flexibility	15
4	Improved virtual communication	11
5	Safe and relaxing virtual environment	11
6	Self-motivation	8
7	Being more responsible	7
8	Eager to adjust in the online learning	5
9	Rate of development similar with face-to-face classes	1

The themes from the responses of the student participants who noted their positive aspects in online learning for their classes were:

Developing new skills and knowledge: A student participant shared his insight in developing his new skills and knowledge with the use of different online learning platforms, “Online classes have been really helpful to me in understanding and learning how to use different sites and platforms especially right now when technology is rapidly advancing.” Another participant expressed in enhancing his creativity in accomplishing his school works, “It helps me to become more creative in all my works.”

Managing time independently: One student noted that e-learning effectively managed his time in completing her school works, as in, “In online learning, I have my time in my hands, and I can create my own schedule and plan what time of the day I am going to do online activities.” This theme is also similar with another student, as he said, “It really helped me to practice time management and prioritize important things.”

Added flexibility: A student expressed that he did not need to wake up early to prepare for his school, “I do not have to wake up early to take a shower, put on clothes, make food, and commute, but instead get on with my classes immediately.” Another student noted that they could still prioritize other things after their online class, for example, “We are able to have our free time to do other things whenever we want.”

Improved virtual communication: One participant noted that she became confident in getting along with her classmates and teachers, “I was able to lessen my uneasiness to interact with others via online since it is our only means of communication in this time of pandemic.” Another participant considered that the interaction within their teacher was uninterrupted, as in, “The communication with our teacher is fast.”

Safe and relaxing virtual environment: A participant stated that studying at home rather than in school should be advisable to prevent the spread of disease, as in, “It is safer for us to study at the comfort of our home rather than having face-to-face interactions especially that we still do not have a vaccine yet against COVID-19.” Another participant felt more relaxed after attending to online class, “I can comfortably sit and rest after class ended immediately.”

Self-motivation: A student expressed that continuing learning is essential for the success of the future career, “I became more persevered to be not left behind and had a chance to discover other online platforms that can be used in the learning.” Another student also felt fulfilled in the online learning, “I have more confidence in myself to understand things.”

Being more responsible: A participant noted that her study habits had been improved during online learning, “It has been helpful to me as a student on how I do not procrastinate things.” In addition to, another student noted that prioritizing her studies is important to increase academic performance, “Online learning made me spend more time on studying by myself.”

Eager to adjust in the online learning: One student showed that he was eager to adjust in the online learning although it was very difficult for him, for example, “Online learning can be challenging for me, but I will be getting used to it.” This is in relation to another opinion, as participant shared, “It helped me to realize that this pandemic cannot stop the education and no matter what happened there is a way.”

Finally, one student mentioned that the rate of development with the online class does not differ with the learning in face-to-face classes. However, the participant was unsure if there has more workload in online classes than the traditional style. He also noted, *"Maybe this is the norm in senior high school, so I am unsure. I need to experience face-to-face classes as a senior high school student before I can conclude whether online learning had been more helpful in my development."*

In Table 9, themes about the negative aspects of online learning were revealed. One hundred and twenty-eight (128) responses were collected on how online learning was not effective for students. It indicates that most of the students experienced technical difficulties when attending to online classes (n=27). Learners are respectively concerned with their mental and physical health issues, as well as being pressured in submitting their school works on deadlines (n=26). Other comments were the following: "difficult to understand a lesson" (n=23); "lack of motivation to study" (n=11); "lack of communication" (n=9); "feeling distracted in a class" (n=3); "expensive cost" (n=2); and "students who have different capabilities" (n=1).

Table 9. Negative aspects of online learning (n=128)

No.	Responses	n
1	Technical difficulties	27
2	Mental and physical health issues	26
3	Pressured in dealing with deadlines	26
4	Difficult to understand a lesson	23
5	Lack of motivation to study	11
6	Lack of communication	9
7	Feeling distracted in a class	3
8	Expensive cost	2
9	Students with different capabilities	1

As shown in Table 9, the themes were identified as the negative aspects to which students had been affected during their online learning:

Technical difficulties: One student responded that their internet connection is unreliable, as in, *"Our internet connection is not that fast and can sometimes get lost."* This concern is similar to another student, as he stated, *"The signal is poor, and sometimes I do not have enough data to access files."*

Mental and physical health issues: A student cited his mental exhaustion which made him difficult to adjust in the online class, *"I could not find a space to breathe or send my mind to clear some things off."* Some students also cited effects on their physical health while being exposed to gadgets, *"Too much exposure to gadgets can cause blurred vision, headaches, and eye strains."*

Pressured in dealing with deadlines: One student participant spoke her struggle in complying school works in terms of deadlines, *"Not all online school works are easy to finish in a short period of time."* Another participant said that she got nervous when they commit to submitting their school works on time, *"I am more worried in passing my school works on time rather than learning the lessons itself."*

Difficult to understand a lesson: A participant expressed dissatisfaction in understanding a lesson in an online class, *"The discussion is sometimes broken and explaining things can be hard especially if you are not talking face to face."* Another participant cited that the lessons were found to be inadequate, *"Lessons and lectures are limited and that is why I could not understand."*

Lack of motivation to study: A student noticed that some of his classmates felt like they did nothing to accomplish an activity, *"Some of the students do not have energy to make the given activity because they feel lazy."* On the other hand, another student felt that she was overloaded as she could not finish those tasks at the same time, *"There are many tasks that I feel like I do not have time for myself."*

Lack of communication: A respondent said that she felt she did not have other people to turn to, *"I have no one to talk to and I cannot actually ask from time to time since the comment section is loaded with questions and comments."* Another respondent favored talking when face-to-face rather than online is important, *"Though we have Messenger to communicate with friends, communicating personally is the best."*

The remaining comments noted the themes of:

- Feeling distracted in a class denoting that some students could not focus on their school works due to other priorities that need to be done.
- Expensive cost considering that the online class required valuable devices and internet plans.
- Students with different capabilities to fit in with the class.

This study determined the positive and negative aspects of online learning brought by the Senior High School students. It is revealed that majority of the students have developed their skills and knowledge when they learn through online; however, they experience technical difficulties that could hinder their learning. These findings agree with Ng (2012) as she noted that the most important reason for teaching students how to use technology is to improve their digital literacy; because the more digital literacy skills and experience a student has, the more versatile and creative he or she can be when using technology to learn or explain what has been learned. Although students have easily adapted to this kind of method, there are challenges that could affect students as they try to reach the interactions between their teachers through the use of technological resources. This shows that students may find themselves more demotivated and anxious because of the lack of access to internet to different online courses and assignments especially the interaction within their co-students and teachers. However, if students believe the learning objectives are more significant, and their technological skill is higher, their interest and satisfaction will increase as well (Kim & Frick, 2011).

Conclusion

Online learning can be a challenge to the learners to succeed in their goals despite the COVID-19 pandemic. Although most Senior High School students perceived that this method is as effective and time-efficient with the traditional learning, there are factors to be considered such as the information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure and their mental and physical well-being.

It is found that the perceptions and attitudes of students are mostly positive, however, home support and assistance should be strongly empowered through the guidance of their parents and family members especially to those who are studying in the private school. While online learning does not mean it can fully replace the traditional learning, it is actually a way to express their concerns and thoughts and to build new friendships that will make the learning environment more interactive and collaborative aside from developing new skills and knowledge to promote their improved performance. Encouraging students to effectively enhance the use of online learning will help them to stay motivated aside from using to different technologies and participating to activities that are suited to their needs and interests.

Teachers should be ready to handle the capabilities of students to grow further in their learning. Educational leaders should have a clear picture on how to adapt, innovate and find creative teaching and learning techniques so that the strengths and opportunities of students will be increased in light with this current situation. Through the proper implementation of learning outcomes, it is best that the members of the academic community should take part in delivering the lessons and activities that are necessary in the curriculum. Future research should also include the impact of the present study to a larger size sample; thus, this will help other researchers to look into alternative ways of promoting effective and time-efficient virtual classrooms.

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